

STUDY OF PROCESS-INDUCED INTERLAMINAR STRESS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY FINE INTEGRATION METHOD

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SUMMARY: A methodology is presented for analyzing the interlaminar thermal stress. The deducing procedure and the formulation of the numerical method is briefly introduced. A study of process-induced interlaminar stress in composite laminates is presented. From the numerical results for typical examples of process-induced interlaminar stress of laminates, it shows that the process induced interlaminar stress fields involves multi-peak values at different stage of curing process. These peaks will be the reason of creation and development of delamination in the laminates during manufacturing process. The method and numerical conclusions given in this paper shall be of values to engineers dealing with the manufacture of composite laminates.

KEYWORDS: interlaminar, stress, curing, fine integration method, simulation and laminates

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that thermal stress occurs in composite laminates when temperature changes. During the curing process in which complex gradient of temperature occurs, significant process-induced interlaminar stress, which can lead to delamination of laminates, can be developed within the laminates. Generally, we may choose plate theories or three-dimensional finite element method (3D-FEM) to solve this kind of problem. However, 3D-FEM can not contend the continuous conditions of interlaminar stress between the sub-layers directly, and because of the introduction of assumptions in the thickness direction, the plate theories are not suit for solving interlaminar stress of laminates either. Thus, there is a strong need to find a new method to solve the interlaminar thermal stress problem of the laminates, especially for the thick laminates. Zhong [1] and Tang [2] have developed a new systematic Hamiltonian methodology for theory of elasticity, which can be used to exactly analyze the interlaminar stress of the laminates.

In the present paper, Hamilton semi-analytical method is further developed in order to solve the interlaminar thermal stress of laminates during curing process. First, the modified Hellinger-Reissner(H-R) functional expression of the thermal elastic problem of composite laminates and the mix-state equations are deduced; Second, a fine integration method is introduced to solve the mix-state equations; Third, as application examples of the method, the process-induced interlaminar stresses of laminates during the curing process are calculated; In

the end, some conclusions are drawn.

THEORITICAL ANALYSIS

1. The modified Hellinger-Reissner(H-R) functional expression

In order to analysis the problem of thermal stress under transient temperature fields, the whole process will be divided into many time steps and incremental expressions is needed in each time step. For thermal elastic problem, the incremental H-R functional expression is

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\Pi_{R_2} = & \iiint_V \left[\Delta S_x \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} - a_x \Delta T \right) + \Delta S_y \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} - a_y \Delta T \right) + \Delta S_z \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta w}{\nabla z} - a_z \Delta T \right) \right. \\
& + \Delta t_{yz} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla z} + \frac{\nabla \Delta w}{\nabla y} \right) + \Delta t_{xz} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla z} + \frac{\nabla \Delta w}{\nabla x} \right) + \Delta t_{xy} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} + \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} - a_{xy} \Delta T \right) \\
& \left. - \frac{1}{2} \{ \Delta S \}^T [S] \{ \Delta S \} \right] dV + \iint_{S_A} \left[(l_n - 1) \Delta P_n (\Delta u_n - \Delta \bar{u}_n) + (l_s - 1) \Delta P_s (\Delta u_s - \Delta \bar{u}_s) \right. \\
& \left. + (l_z - 1) \Delta P_z (\Delta w - \Delta \bar{w}) - l_n \Delta \bar{P}_n \Delta u_n - l_s \Delta \bar{P}_s \Delta u_s - l_z \Delta \bar{P}_z \Delta w \right] dS \quad (1)
\end{aligned}$$

where, v is the volume; $\{ \Delta S \} = \{ \Delta S_x \ \Delta S_y \ \Delta S_z \ \Delta t_{yz} \ \Delta t_{xz} \ \Delta t_{xy} \}^T$ is the incremental stress vector; Δu , Δv and Δw are the incremental displacement components; a_x, a_y, a_z and a_{xy} are the thermal expansion coefficients in the x, y and z directions and a coupling coefficient, respectively; $[S]$ is the compliance matrix for the i th sublaminates; subscripts n, s and z represent the normal, shear and thickness directions of boundaries of plates, respectively; l_n, l_s and l_z are boundary characteristic parameters in n, s and z directions, respectively, so that e.g. for the direction n , if $S_A \in S_s$ then $l_n = 1$, whereas if $S_A \in S_u$ then $l_n = 0$; where, S_s and S_u are the traction and displacement boundaries, respectively; $\Delta \bar{p}_n, \Delta \bar{p}_s$ and $\Delta \bar{p}_z$ are the incremental boundary traction in the n, s and z directions, respectively.

Using the variation scheme, $\partial \Delta \Pi_R / \partial \Delta S_x = \partial \Delta \Pi_R / \partial \Delta S_y = \partial \Delta \Pi_R / \partial \Delta t_{xy} = 0$, which gives

$$\begin{Bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ t_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = [S^*]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \nabla u / \nabla x - S_{13} S_z \\ \nabla v / \nabla y - S_{23} S_z \\ \nabla u / \nabla y + \nabla v / \nabla x - S_{36} S_z \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} T_x \\ T_y \\ T_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} T_x \\ T_y \\ T_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = [S^*]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \Delta T, \quad [S^*] = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{16} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{26} \\ S_{16} & S_{26} & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

and T_x, T_y and T_{xy} are the equivalent traction due to the change of temperature ΔT . Substituting Eqn.2 into Eqn.1, and assuming state vectors $\{ \Delta q \} = \{ \Delta u \ \Delta v \ \Delta w \}^T$ and $\{ \Delta p \} = \{ \Delta t_{xz} \ \Delta t_{yz} \ \Delta S_z \}^T$, The modified H-R functional expression can be deduced as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \Pi_R^* = & \int_{z_i}^{z_{i+1}} \left\{ \iint_{\Omega} (\{\Delta p\}^T \{\Delta \dot{q}\} - \Delta H) dx dy + \oint_{S_L} [(l_n - 1) \Delta P_n (\Delta u_n - \Delta \bar{u}_n) \right. \\ & + (l_s - 1) \Delta P_s (\Delta u_s - \Delta \bar{u}_s) + (l_z - 1) \Delta P_z (\Delta w - \Delta \bar{w}) \\ & \left. - l_n \Delta \bar{p}_n \Delta u_n - l_s \Delta \bar{p}_s \Delta u_s - l_z \Delta \bar{p}_z \Delta w] dS \right\} dz \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, Ω is the plane area, S_L is the perimeter and $\{\Delta \dot{q}\} = (\partial/\partial z)\{\Delta u \quad \Delta v \quad \Delta w\}^T$. ΔH is the Hamiltonian function, which can be expressed as [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H = & -\frac{1}{2} c_{11} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} c_{22} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} c_{33} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} + \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} \right)^2 - c_{12} \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \\ & - c_{13} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} + \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} \right) - c_{23} \left(\frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} + \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} \right) - t_{yz} \frac{\nabla \Delta w}{\nabla y} \\ & - t_{xz} \frac{\nabla \Delta w}{\nabla x} + \Delta S_z \left(D_1 \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} + D_3 \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} + D_3 \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} + D_2 \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \bar{S}_{33} \Delta S_z^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} S_{44} \Delta t_{yz}^2 + \frac{1}{2} S_{55} \Delta t_{xz}^2 + S_{45} \Delta t_{xz} \Delta t_{yz} + \Delta f_x \Delta u + \Delta f_y \Delta v + \Delta f_z \Delta w - C_a \Delta T^2 \\ & + \left[\left(T_x \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla x} + T_{xy} \frac{\nabla \Delta u}{\nabla y} \right) + \left(T_{xy} \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla x} + T_y \frac{\nabla \Delta v}{\nabla y} \right) + \bar{a}_z \Delta S_z \right] \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

in which, c_{ij} (i,j=1,2,3) are the component of the inverse of the matrix $[S^*]$, and

$$\{D_1 \quad D_2 \quad D_3\}^T = [S^*]^{-1} \{S_{13} \quad S_{23} \quad S_{36}\}^T \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{S}_{33} = S_{33} - \{S_{13} \quad S_{23} \quad S_{36}\} [S^*]^{-1} \{S_{13} \quad S_{23} \quad S_{36}\}^T \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{a}_z = a_z - S_{13} T_x - S_{23} T_y - S_{36} T_{xy} \quad (8)$$

2. Mix-state equations

Discretizing the state vectors $\{\Delta q\}$ and $\{\Delta p\}$ from Eqn.4 in the x-y coordinate plane gives

$$\{\Delta q\} = [N(x, y)] \{\Delta q(z)\}^e, \quad \{\Delta p\} = [N(x, y)] \{\Delta p(z)\}^e \quad (9)$$

where $[N(x, y)]$ is the shape function matrix $\{\Delta q(z)\}^e$ and $\{\Delta p(z)\}^e$ are the incremental node state vectors of the element, which are the functions only of the variable z. Substituting Eqn.9 into the modified H-R functional expression of Eqn.4, and then through the variation procedure gives the following mixed state finite element equation for the *i*th sublaminates:

$$[C]^e \frac{d}{dz} \{\Delta d(z)\}^e = [K]^e \{\Delta d(z)\}^e + \{\Delta f(z)\}^e \quad (10)$$

where, $\{\Delta d(z)\}^e = \left\{ \left\{ \Delta q(z)^e \right\}^T \quad \left\{ \Delta p(z)^e \right\}^T \right\}^T$, and the detailed expression of matrix $[C]^e$ and $[K]^e$ and the vector $\{\Delta f(z)\}^e$ (and for $[A]_i$ and the $\{\Delta F(z)\}_{f_i}$ below) are so complicated that they are omitted here.

Assembling all the finite elements in the i th sublaminar gives the mixed state equation as:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \{\Delta d(z)\}_{f_i} = [A]_i \{\Delta d(z)\}_{f_i} + \{\Delta F(z)\}_{f_i} \quad (11)$$

where, $\{\Delta d(z)\}_{f_i} = \sum_e \{\Delta d(z)\}^e$.

3. Fine integration answer of mixed state equation

The analytical solution of Eqn.11 for the first order differential equation for the vector $\{\Delta d(z)\}_{f_i}$ is

$$\{\Delta d(z)\}_{f_i} = [T(z)]_i \{\Delta d(0)\}_{f_i} + \{\Delta Q(z)\}_{f_i} \quad (12)$$

where, $[T(z)]_i = \exp\{[A]_i \cdot z\}$, and $\{\Delta Q(z)\}_{f_i} = \int_0^z \exp\{[A]_i(z-t)\} \{\Delta F(t)\}_{f_i} dt$. The continuity condition between the i th and $(i+1)$ th sublaminar gives,

$$\{\Delta d(h_i)\}_{f_i} = \{\Delta d(0)\}_{f_{i+1}} \quad (13)$$

Using the transfer matrix scheme [3], the formula relating the state vector $\{\Delta d\}$ at the top and bottom surface of the laminate can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\Delta d(h_n)\}_{f_n} = & [\Pi_{i=n}^1 [T]_i] \{\Delta d(0)\}_{f_1} + [\Pi_{i=n}^2 [T]_i] \{\Delta Q(h_1)\}_{f_1} + [\Pi_{i=n}^3 [T]_i] \{\Delta Q(h_2)\}_{f_2} + \dots \\ & + [\Pi_{i=n}^n [T]_i] \{\Delta Q(h_{n-1})\}_{f_{n-1}} + \{\Delta Q(h_n)\}_{f_n} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where, $\Pi_{i=n}^n [T]_i = [T]_n [T]_{n-1} \dots [T]_i \dots [T]_2 [T]_1$. Eqn.14 can alternatively be written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta q(h_n) \\ \Delta p(h_n) \end{Bmatrix}_{f_n} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta q(0) \\ \Delta p(0) \end{Bmatrix}_{f_1} + \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta Q_q \\ \Delta Q_p \end{Bmatrix}_{f_n} \quad (15)$$

where $\left\{ \Delta q(h_n)^T \quad \Delta p(h_n)^T \right\}_{f_n}^T$ and $\left\{ \Delta q(0)^T \quad \Delta p(0)^T \right\}_{f_1}^T$ are the state vectors in the top and bottom surface, respectively; and $\left\{ \Delta Q_q^T \quad \Delta Q_p^T \right\}_{f_n}^T$ is the corresponding known incremental vector which is contributed by the incremental thermal loading, and the incremental induced boundary displacements and tractions.

Generally, half of the components of the incremental state vectors of the top and/or bottom surface of the laminates are known and so the other half can be determined from Eqn.15. After the incremental state vectors on the top and bottom surface of the laminates are obtained, all the incremental state vectors and in-plane stress vectors at any position of the laminates can be computed from Eqn.12 and Eqn.2, respectively.

4. The transient thermal stress and displacement

For any time step i , the above incremental analysis procedures can be used and the incremental stress vector $\{\Delta S\}_i$ can be solved. Let $\{S\}_{i-1}$ represent the total stress vector at the $(i-1)$ th time step. Then the corresponding value at the i th time step is:

$$\{S\}_i = \{S\}_{i-1} + \{\Delta S\}_i \quad (16)$$

The transient stress can be obtained by adding the incremental stress step by step, so long as the time step is sufficient small.

EXAMPLES

1. Interlaminar stress of laminates during cooling down process

Fig 1 shows a laminates, the dimension is $100 \times 100 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$, the material properties are $l_L = 2.4 (W/(m^2K))$, $l_T = 0.62 (W/(m^2K))$, $r = 2.007 \text{ kg/cm}^3$, $C_p = 1100 (J/(kg.K))$, $a_L = 2.85 (\times 10^{-6}/C)$, $a_T = a_Z = 19.8 (\times 10^{-6}/C)$, where $E_L = 206.08 (Gpa)$, $E_T = E_Z = 7.75 (Gpa)$, $G_{LT} = G_{LZ} = 1.78 (Gpa)$, $G_{TZ} = 2.76786 (Gpa)$, $\eta_{LT} = \eta_{LZ} = 0.2$, $\eta_{TZ} = 0.4$, The subscripts L , T represent the longitudinal and transverse directions of the fiber, respectively, where the subscripts Z represent the thickness directions of the sublaminates. The plying angle is 0° . The transient thermal stresses of the laminates are calculated during the period of the surface temperature of laminates cooling down from $177^\circ C$ to $24^\circ C$ in 15 minutes till all the sublaminates temperature reaches the same. The temperature fields are calculated using the method in reference [4], The results of the thermal interlaminar stress in the center sublaminates at the point $(x=0, y=0)$ of the laminates are shown in Fig2 to Fig.4.

Fig. 1. Geometry of laminate.

Fig. 2 Result of stress σ_x in the center sublaminate

Fig.3 Result of stress τ_{yx} in the center sublaminate

Fig.4 Result of stress τ_{xz} in the center sublaminate

2. Interlaminar stress of laminates during the whole curing process

Consider $[0^0/0^0]_{4s}$ and $[+45^0/-45^0]_{4s}$ glass/polyester composites laminates with $a=b=50\text{cm}$, $t=0.5\text{cm}$ and $d=t/16$ as show in Fig 1. Assuming the constituent glass and polyester to be isotropic, the material properties are [5]: for the fiber, $E_f = 7.038 \times 10^4 (\text{Mpa})$, $G_f = 2.992 \times 10^4 (\text{Mpa})$, $m_f = 0.2$ and $a_f = 5.04 (\times 10^{-6} / \text{C})$, and for the resin, $m_m = 0.4$, $a_m = 7.20 (\times 10^{-5} / \text{C})$, and E_m and G_m are compute from the equation:

$$E_m = (1 - \alpha) E_m^0 + E_m^c, G_m = E_m / 2(1 + m_m) \quad (17)$$

where α is the cure degree, which can be obtained from the simulation of reference [4]; E_m^0 and E_m^c are the assumed initial cross-linking and the fully cured temperature dependent resin moduli, respectively. Here, it is assumed $E_m^0 = 2.757 \text{Mpa}$ and $E_m^c = 2.757 \times 10^3 \text{Mpa}$ [5]. Let

the value of fiber friction of sublaminates be 54% and the typical temperature curing cycle for the composite to be as illustrated in Fig.5. Fig.6 to Fig.8 gives numerical results for the process-induced interlaminar stress at the center points of the surface between the two middle sublaminates during the curing process. The solid lines refer to the $[0^0/0^0]_{4s}$ laminates and the dotted lines refer to $[+45^0/-45^0]_{4s}$ laminates.

Fig. 5 Curing cycle for glass/polyester composite.

Fig. 6 σ_z at $z=h$.

Fig. 7 τ_{yz} at $z=0$.

Fig. 8 τ_{xz} at $z=0$.

CONCLUSIONS

The complex gradients and multi-peak values of process-induced thermal interlaminar stresses will occur in the laminates during the whole curing process. This process-induced interlaminar stress would contribute significantly to initial delamination, the growth of crack and the deformation of the laminates and thus decrease mechanical properties and carrying capacity of the laminates.

The modified Hellinger-Reissner variational principle and the corresponding fine integration method provide an efficient way to investigate the interlaminar thermal stress of laminates. Because the discontinuous in-plane stresses are eliminated from H-R functional expression and the continuity of displacement and interlaminar stress components between the sub-laminates are both strictly satisfied. And because the finite element method is combined with the exact integration, the method is suitable for calculating the process-induced interlaminar stress in both thin and thick laminates.

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